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Impact of Green Products on the Health and Wellness of Consumers in India

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Abstract

Consumers all over the world considered green product as any product which has lesser environmental harmful impacts as compared to any other product with similar function or application. Consumers at global level have shown the intense loyalty towards a company which is environmental friendly, committed to social values and willing to pay more for the products being made from fresh, natural and/or organic ingredients. In recent years, there has been a growing global awareness of the environmental and health implications associated with conventional consumer products. This has led to an increased demand for eco-friendly or "green" alternatives across various industries. This research explores the multifaceted impact of green products on the health and wellness of consumers. Furthermore, the research investigates the psychological aspects of consumer choices, exploring how the perception of using green products may positively affect mental well-being. The data were collected through multistage random sampling. Using an interview schedule, data was collected from 104 respondents from 52 wards. The secondary data were collected from journals, books, reports, unpublished and published materials. The primary data were processed using appropriate statistical techniques in particular concerning the percentage method, ANOVA, and garret ranking technique. The findings from this research are expected to provide valuable insights for policymakers, businesses, and consumers alike. As the global community strives to address pressing environmental issues, this study contributes to the ongoing discourse surrounding the interconnectedness of sustainable practices, consumer health, and overall well-being.

Key Words: Green Products, Health, Wellness, Consumers, Ecological, Environment.

Introduction

The ecological advantages of green products are evident in their reduced carbon footprint, minimized use of harmful chemicals, and emphasis on recyclability. Green products are often formulated with fewer harmful chemicals, which can reduce consumers' exposure to potentially hazardous substances. Studies like those by Liu et al. and Smith et al. have highlighted the link between exposure to certain chemicals in traditional products and adverse health effects. Patel et al. (2018), suggest that using green products may have positive effects on mental health. The psychological benefits of choosing environmentally friendly options might contribute to overall well-being. However, their impact on individual health remains a nuanced and evolving aspect of research. By scrutinizing the composition and attributes of green products, we can unravel how these choices influence personal well-being, considering factors such as exposure to toxins, allergens, and the broader implications for mental health. Smith and Brown (2012) delved into consumer motivations for choosing sustainable products but predominantly focused on the socio-psychological aspects, leaving a gap in understanding the tangible health outcomes associated with such choices. This current study, by contrast, seeks to bridge this gap by exploring both the psychological and physiological dimensions of the impact of green products on consumer health. Pioneering research by Jones et al. (2018) explored the environmental benefits of green products, emphasizing reduced carbon emissions and sustainable sourcing. While their work laid a crucial foundation, the current study extends this perspective by examining the reciprocal relationship between green products and consumer health. Recognizing the interconnectedness of environmental sustainability and human well-being, our research aims to fill the void by exploring the health implications associated with adopting green alternatives.

Statement of the Problem

While some studies have explored the psychological motivations behind the selection of sustainable products, a comprehensive examination of how these choices impact mental well-being is lacking. This research aims to unravel the intricate interplay between consumer psychology, environmental responsibility, and individual health outcomes associated with the use of green products. Therefore, it's important to find the impact of green products on the health and wellness of consumers.

Objectives

1. To identify the impact of green products on health issues.
2. To identify the Wellness the respondents, acquire from green products.

Methodology

Research Design

Mixed-Methods Approach: This study is an empirical one based on the survey method. Primary data were collected with the help of a well-structured questionnaire. The data was collected from 104 respondents from 52. Out of 52 wards, the researcher has chosen two sample respondents from each ward. By using multistage random sampling, the researcher has collected data. The data were processed using appropriate statistical techniques in particular concerning the percentage method, ANOVA, and garret ranking technique.

Analysis

Age-Wise Classification

Table .1 Age-Wise Classification

S.No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1.	Below 20 years	4	3.8
2.	21-30 years	61	58.7
3.	31-40 years	24	23.1
4.	41-50 years	11	10.6
5.	Above 50 years	4	3.8
	Total	104	100

Primary data

Table 1 shows that 3.8 percent (4) of the respondents are in the age group of below 20 years and equal percent of the respondents are in the age group of above 50 years. And 58.7 percent (61) of the respondents belong to age group of 21-30 years. It is clear that most of the adults have knowledge about green products. With the help of ANOVA test age of the respondents an Impact of green products on their health is tested with following hypothesis.

**Table 2
Age Concerning the Impact of Green Products on Health Issues**

S.No	Health Issues	Age of the respondents					F value	P value
		Below 20	21-30	31-40	41-50	Above 50		
1	Blood pressure	5.00 (0.000)	3.41 (1.283)	3.54 (1.103)	4.27 (1.009)	4.00 (1.155)	2.762	.032*
2	Diabetes	4.00 (1.155)	3.25 (1.234)	3.29 (1.160)	4.27 (1.009)	4.00 (1.155)	3.881	.006**
3	Cholesterol	3.00 (1.826)	3.77 (1.039)	3.58 (1.060)	3.09 (1.136)	3.00 (1.826)	2.912	.025*
4	Headache	4.50 (.577)	3.46 (1.205)	3.25 (1.113)	3.82 (1.079)	4.00 (1.155)	2.381	.057
5	Skin Allergies	4.00 (1.155)	3.41 (1.160)	3.21 (1.103)	3.91 (1.375)	4.00 (1.155)	2.704	.035*
6	Eye problems	3.00 (1.826)	3.54 (1.134)	3.04 (.806)	2.27 (1.009)	4.50 (.577)	7.986	.000**
7	Ear problems	3.00 (1.826)	3.13 (1.218)	3.25 (1.152)	2.45 (1.128)	4.50 (.577)	4.863	.001**
8	Cold and cough	3.00 (1.826)	3.59 (.883)	3.46 (.833)	2.73 (1.191)	2.50 (1.732)	5.782	.000**
9	Breathing issues	5.00 (0.000)	3.39 (1.021)	3.13 (.947)	3.82 (1.079)	4.00 (1.155)	3.764	.007**
10	Tooth ache	4.50 (.577)	3.07 (1.093)	3.29 (.955)	2.82 (1.250)	3.75 (.957)	3.804	.006**
11	Stomach ache	3.00 (1.826)	3.13 (1.132)	2.71 (.908)	2.91 (1.700)	4.50 (.577)	5.173	.001**
12	Hair issues	4.00 (1.155)	3.46 (1.119)	3.58 (1.018)	2.64 (.809)	3.25 (2.062)	3.658	.008*
13	Constipation	5.00 (0.000)	3.25 (1.105)	3.08 (1.213)	3.82 (1.079)	4.00 (1.155)	3.494	.010*
14	Weight loss	4.50 (.577)	3.43 (1.132)	3.17 (1.090)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	3.060	.020*

15	Weight gain	3.00 (1.826)	3.02 (1.088)	2.96 (.999)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	4.846	.001**
16	Back pain	4.00 (1.155)	3.02 (1.147)	3.13 (1.076)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	4.188	.004**
17	Indigestion	4.00 (1.155)	3.13 (1.040)	3.08 (.974)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	4.436	.002**
18	Vitamin deficiency	5.00 (0.000)	3.16 (1.128)	3.25 (1.152)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	3.454	.011*
19	Inability to sleep	3.00 (1.826)	3.41 (1.309)	3.00 (1.142)	3.27 (1.679)	4.50 (.577)	2.920	.025*
20	Facial problems	4.00 (1.155)	3.36 (1.239)	3.33 (1.204)	3.36 (1.567)	4.50 (.577)	2.443	.052

Source: Statistically analysed data Notes: * denotes significance at a 5 per cent level ** denotes significance at a 1 per cent level

The null hypothesis is rejected at a 1 per cent level with regard to eye problems, ear problems, colds, stomach aches, toothache, hair issues, back pain, indigestion, weight gain, diabetes, and breathing issues. The null hypothesis is rejected at a 5 per cent level regarding blood pressure, cholesterol, skin allergies, vitamin deficiency, Inability to sleep, weight loss, and constipation. It is inferred that the impact of green products on health issues is different for all age groups. In the case of 'headache' and 'facial problem,' the p-value is greater than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted at a 5 per cent level. Therefore, there is no significant difference among age groups with respect to 'headache' and 'facial problem'.

Wellness the Respondents Acquire From Green Products

Respondents often acquire a sense of wellness and various health benefits from using green products. Here are some ways in which respondents may experience wellness benefits from using green products:

Table - 3
Wellness the Respondents Acquire From Green Products

S.No	Particulars	Garret mean score	Rank
1.	I feel happy	3.18	II
2.	I feel Stress free	4.24	I
3.	I am able to give maximum Productivity	3.08	III
4.	I keep up good health	2.82	IV
5.	I am able to maintain my natural beauty	2.51	X
6.	I am able to handle my depression	2.62	IX
7.	I am free from Infections	2.92	V
8.	I tackle my anger	2.66	VIII
9.	My self-image is improved	2.82	VI
10.	I am very confident	2.78	VII

Source: Computed data

Table shows that, wellness the respondents acquire from green products 'personal hygienic products' ranked first with the mean score of 5.52, followed by 'cosmetics' with the mean score 5.43 ranked second. The least score of 2.54 ranked tenth for 'kitchen equipment'. Hence it is interpreted that personal hygienic products and cosmetics being the most preferred, while kitchen equipment is the least preferred among the surveyed respondents. This suggests that respondents are less inclined to purchase green kitchen equipment compared to other categories.

Findings

1. The higher percentage in this age group indicates a notable awareness or familiarity with environmentally sustainable products among individuals in their twenties and early thirties.
2. There is no significant difference between age and the impact of green products on health issues. The above null hypothesis is rejected at 1% level with regards to eye problems, ear problems, cold, stomach ache, tooth ache, hair issues, back pain, indigestion, weight gain, diabetes and breathing issues. The null hypothesis is rejected at 5% level with regards to blood pressure, cholesterol, skin allergies, vitamin deficiency, Inability to sleep, weight loss and constipation. It is inferred that impact of green products on health issues are different for all age groups. In the case of 'headache' and 'facial problem' the p value is greater than 0.05 the null hypothesis is accepted at 5 per cent level. Therefore, there is no significant difference among age group with respect to 'headache' and 'facial problem'.
3. The wellness the respondents acquire from green products 'personal hygienic products' ranked first with the mean score of 5.52, followed by 'cosmetics' with the mean score 5.43 ranked second. The least score of 2.54 ranked tenth for 'kitchen equipment'. Hence it is interpreted that personal hygienic products and cosmetics being the most preferred, while kitchen equipment is the least preferred among the surveyed respondents. This suggests that respondents are less inclined to purchase green kitchen equipment compared to other categories.

Suggestions

1. Implement engagement strategies such as social media campaigns, influencer collaborations, and interactive content that resonate with individuals in their twenties and early thirties. This age group is likely to be more active on social platforms and responsive to visually appealing and engaging content.
2. Develop educational initiatives or informational content that not only promotes your products but also raises awareness about the environmental impact of consumer choices. This can further strengthen the association between your brand and eco-conscious decision-making.
3. Marketers can create targeted campaigns that highlight how green products can address specific health issues within various age groups. Tailoring product information and marketing materials to address the unique concerns of different age demographics can be more effective.
4. Government agencies can work on establishing guidelines and regulations that ensure the effectiveness and safety of green products, particularly those marketed for health-related issues. This can help build consumer trust in these products.
5. Implement targeted marketing and awareness campaigns specifically focusing on the environmental benefits and features of green kitchen equipment. Highlight how these products contribute to sustainability and appeal to the eco-conscious values of consumers.
6. Create informative content that educates consumers about the positive environmental impact of choosing green kitchen equipment. Emphasize energy efficiency, eco-friendly materials, and any other sustainable practices associated with these products.

Conclusion

The environmental protection is essential. People believe a green life is a restored and healthier life. Most consumers buying patterns show that they have a desire for brands that go green. Consumers not only want to buy their green products but also, need to pay the correct money for them. Green marketing is a tool for protecting the environment for the future it has a positive impact on environmental safety. Green marketing is not only an environmental protection it also protects the health and wellness of consumers.

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